

An Ethnographic Exploration of the Customary Laws of The Deori Tribe of Majuli

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Abstract

Deori is one of the major tribes who have made an immense contribution to the formation of greater Assamese culture. They are unique among the other tribes by their customs, dress pattern, food habits, rituals and rites and they prefer to live within the periphery of traditions, firm rules and regulations of customs. The tribe is one of the major inhabitants of Majuli district and has a rich heritage of customary laws that regulates social, religious and economic aspects of life. The objectives of the study are to know the importance of customary laws among the Deori tribe and to study its role in social sphere of the Deori tribe of Majuli. The study is conducted in Deori Pam and Major Deori villages of Majuli district. The two villages are selected through purposive sampling and the purpose of choosing of these two villages is that the Deori people of Majuli belong to the Dibongiya sub group and this sub group is still maintaining their customs, culture and language. The study is based on both primary and secondary sources. Primary data has been collected by interviewing the elderly persons of the community. Secondary data has been collected from secondary sources like books and journals. The study has shown that, the tribe strongly believes that customary laws can preserve their traditional knowledge, culture, morals and govern their social life. The study shows that they maintain a unique system of

dispute settlement, inheritance, marriage and community governance through oral tradition and religious sanction.

Key words: Deori, Tribe, Customary law, Ethnographic Study, Majuli.

Introduction:

The North Eastern Region of India is considered as a land of cultural paradise where people live a very simple mode of life by maintaining their identity all the way through practicing traditions and customs from the time immemorial. Indeed, this region presents glorious socio-cultural and religious traits of diverse tribal and non tribal ethnic groups and customs are playing immense influence on their life. Human being expects peace and order, control and stability in society for all times. By the mechanisms like folkways, mores and customs people try to preserve peace and order in society. Among these mechanisms customary law is considered as the most influential and powerful mode for continuation of social control.

Deori is one of the major tribes who have made an immense contribution to the formation of greater Assamese culture. Like other tribes and communities, the Indian Constitution has considered Deori as the Scheduled Tribe of Assam. They are unique among the other tribes by their customs, dress pattern, food habits, rituals and rites. The Deori people prefer to live within the periphery of traditions, firm rules and regulations of customs.

Concept of Custom and Customary Law

Customs are very much dominant to our life. Though, in the modern complex society it is slowly losing its importance, yet in the tribal life still it is playing a significant role. According to Oxford English Dictionary, custom is a traditional and widely accepted way of behaving or doing something that is specific to a particular society, place and time. The origin of custom is obscure, because it is difficult to ascertain the accurate way through which it emerged. The

Sociologists believe that the origin lies in habits and it grew into customs through practice, imitation and acceptance of values. “The word custom” as defined by Sapir, “is used to apply to the totality of behavior patterns which are carried by tradition and lodged in the group, as contrasted with mere random personal activities of the individual. Radin states that “customs are regarded as habitual ways of conduct among social groups (Mohanti, K. 2004).

A custom become law when the whole members of community or tribes show respects to it and follow it as part of their society. Customary law can be termed as a set of rules that attain the force of law because a society observes them continuously and uniformly for a long time. This totality of a tribe’s customs handed over from one generation to the next provides rules, enforcement procedures and punishment for violations (Singh, 1993). Customary laws are believed as an essential part of social life. These are some unwritten rules which have been developed from the customs and traditions of communities. Most of the tribes of the North Eastern Region consider their customary laws intrinsic to their identity and part and parcel of their culture and tradition. It has been playing a big role in keeping peace and order in society.

Concept of Tribe

In sociology, generally a tribe refers to a group of people characterized by common decent, a common name, shared culture, common language or dialect, shared customs and a common territory. Tribe typically practices subsistence activities like hunting, fishing, shifting cultivation, or small scale agriculture. According to the 2011 Census report of India, the scheduled Tribe population is 10.43 crore which is 8.6% of India’s population. About 89.97% of scheduled tribe live in rural areas and 10.03% live in urban areas. Scheduled tribes are identified as historically disadvantaged communities, both socially and economically and they are considered deserving of special support and protection. The north eastern region is particularly significant because this region has one of the highest concentrations of tribal communities of the country. States like Mizoram, Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh and Manipur have majority of arge tribal people, while Assam and Tripura also have important tribal population. The tribes of this

region viz. *Khasi, Jayantita, Naga, Bodo Kachari, Sonowa Kachari, Tripuri, Deori, Karbi, Kuki, Garo* etc. each with unique customs and traditions.

Deories of Assam

The Deori is one of the major ethnic tribes of Assam and Arunachal Pradesh. This ethnic group is the priest class of the Chutia community. Hussain states in his book 'Asomor Sankhpta Itihash' that the Deori Chutia is the priest class of the whole Chutia community and only this class is the custodian of the language, religion and customs of the Chutia community. The Deori people of Assam are basically a clan of Tibeto-Mongolian group. This ethnic group has three sub groups viz. Dibongiyas, Borgonyas and Tengapaniyas. The Patorgonyas was also known as a subgroup of Deori tribe, but in later periods the Patorgoyans assimilated with Dibongiyas (Goswami, 1991, 89). Among these three Deori subgroups the Dibongiyas are maintaining their traditional rituals, dress pattern, food habits, folk tales, customs and language through centuries. The Tengaponiyas and Borgoyans assimilated into the Assamese culture by adopting Assamese language and culture (Nandeswar Deori and Karabi Deori, 2009, 17). Except the Dibongiya sub groups, others have lost their language due to the geographical diversity (Khagen Ch. Deori, 2001).

The Deori ethnic tribe lived on the bank of Kundil River, which flows through Kundil Nagar (now Sadiya). They were leading a prosperous and peaceful life in Sadiya. Most of them left Sadiya in 1829-30 when their nearby hill tribes Khamti and Misimi invaded them (Nandeswar Deori and Karabi Deori, 2009, 10-11). During that time their way was to an uncertain destination sailing through the river the Brahmaputra. They reached different places on bank of the river and had tried to continue their traditions by establishing *Deoghor*¹ and practicing rituals in Deoghor. Now the Deori inhabitants are found mostly in Lakhimpur, Dhemaji, Jorhat, Sivasagar, Tinsukia and Majuli Dstricts of Upper Assam. According to 2011

¹ temple of the Deori tribe

Census, the total population of Deori tribe is 43,750 (this figure constitutes 1.13% of the total population in the states.) which composed 21,938 males and 21,812 females.

Deori Tribe of Majuli:

Majuli, located in the Brahmaputra River, is the world's largest river island. The island had a total area of 1,250 square kilometers at the beginning of 20th century, but due to erosion, now, it had an area of 352 square kilometer. The island is shaped by the river Brahmaputra in the south and the Kherkatia Xuti, an anabranch of the Brhamaputra in the north. According to the census report 2011, the total population of Majuli is 167,304 and density of population is 300 per square kilometer. The dwellers of Majuli are mostly of the Mishing tribe. The other inhabitants of Majuli are Deori, Sonowal Kachari, Chutia, Ahom, Kalita, Kaibartta etc.

The Deori Tribe is one of the major inhabitants of Majuli. The Deori people inhabitant villages of Majuli are *Major Deori Gaon* and *Deori Pam Gaon*. Majority of Deori people reside in Major Deori village. According to the Census of India (2011), the total population of Major Deori village is 1,638, comprising 842 males and 796 females, with a sex ratio of 945 females per 1,000 males. Of this population, approximately 1,370 individuals belong to the Scheduled Tribes, while a smaller proportion is from the Scheduled Castes. The village consists of about 281 households. Similarly, the total population of Deori Pam village is 385, including 202 males and 183 females, resulting in a sex ratio of 905 females per 1,000 males (Census, 2011). Out of the total, 368 persons are from the Scheduled Tribes, and the village comprises 64 households. A comparative analysis shows that while Major Deori village has a significantly larger population and numbers of households, both villages demonstrate a high concentration of Scheduled Tribe residents, reflecting the strong demographic presence of the Deori community in Majuli district.

Basically in both Major Deori and Deori Pam villages of Majuli, the Deori people belong to the Dibongiya sub group (Khagen Ch. Deori, 2001). The Dibongiya sub group has eight clans viz. *Boderi* or *Bordeori*, *Kumtai*, *Aairio*, *Patiroi*, *Lagachuyo*, *Chchario*, *Sitigai* and *Komar*. Their chief religious priest is chosen from the *Boderi* or *Bordeori*. If the *Bordeori* clan is not available in village, their priest is chosen from the *Kumta* clan. In the absence of both *Bordeori* and *Kumta*

clan the priest is chosen from the *Komar* clan. The centre of art and culture of Deori people is Deoghor where they perform religious ceremonies. The priest class of Deori people is called Degor Poria. On the basis of authority the priest class is divided into eight viz. *Boderi* or *Bordeori*, *Soderi* or *Sarudeori*, *Borborali*, *Soruborali*, *Bora*, *Barik*, *Kelua Bora* and *Randhoni*. These all priest classes perform their traditional customs and rules and regulation through the religious and cultural activities of *Deoghor*. The tribe has a rich heritage of customary laws that regulates social, religious and economic aspects of their life. They maintain a unique system of dispute settlement, inheritance, marriage and community governance through oral tradition and religious sanction.

Ethnographic Study

An ethnographic study is a qualitative research method used mainly in Anthropology, sociology and cultural studies to understand people or group of people, their culture and their everyday practices. The word ethnography comes from Greek words 'ethnos' and 'graphy' which mean people or culture and writing or description accordingly. Ethnographic study is based on field work, participant observation, in-depth understanding and interpretation. Through this research method researcher tries to understand tradition, culture, language, rituals, laws, social relations etc. and describes not just what people do but why they do it within the periphery of their community or cultural group.

Objectives

The objectives of the study are to know the importance of customary laws among the Deori tribe and to study its role in social sphere of the Deori tribe of Majuli.

Methodology

This is an ethnographic study and conducted in Deori Pam and Maajor Deori villages of Majuli district. The two villages are selected through purposive sampling. The purpose of

choosing of these two villages is that the Deori people of Majuli belong to the Dibongiya sub group and this sub group continues to maintain their customs, culture and language whereas the other sub-groups of Deori tribe do not.

The study is based on both primary and secondary sources. Primary data has been collected by interviewing the elderly persons of the community, observation, field work and secondary data has been collected from secondary sources like books, journals and Governmental reports.

Customary law among the Deori tribe of Majuli

Deori tribe is very different in customary practices. Investigations in the field revealed that there is no any written customs or constitution in Deori society, but from the time immemorial they have been following traditional religion, festivals and ways of worshipping God, funeral activities, marriage relationships and tenets of punishment for the offenders or lawbreakers. The Deori people are custom lovers and they believe that their cultural life, religious features and social aspects can be reflected through their customs. The Deori people always try to uphold their traditional customs for the sake of smooth functioning of their society. Nobody can be relieved from the punishment given by their elders and chief of their village, if someone breaks their social customs, disobeys their elders, establishes socially forbidden marriage relationship, keeps extra marital affairs and kills cow. He or she must repent for their misdeeds or otherwise might be excommunicate forever. A meeting (*mel*) is organized in their village and in the presence of their highly regarded village person viz. Bordeori, Barik, Bharali, Gaonburha, the quantity of punishment are decided for the offender or lawbreaker.

a. Customary law among the tribe in personal sphere

In the milieu of family, their most important customary law is related to maintain the inter relationship and duties of family members towards one another. Among the Deori people of Major Deori village, there is some definite code of conduct which to be followed by the members of their society. It is the general duty for younger members to respect and obey their

parents and elders of their family. According to them, hurting parents and elders is a great sin. If someone disobeys or hurts their parents and elders, he or she has to repent in front of his parents or elders. For such type of fault, one must confess in the presence of their parents or elders, highly regarded person of their society viz. Bordeori, Barik and Bharali and confer penalty to the elders of the village.

b. Prohibitive Marriage

Deori tribe considers marriage as sacred ritual. They have been maintaining certain laws and practices which govern the institution of marriage. These are mainly the rule of *gotro* and clan exogamy and other kinds of marriages. According to the Deori people of both Major Deori and Deori Pam village that marriage relation can be established between the members of the three sub groups *Tengaponiya*, *Borgoyan* and *Dibongiya*. Marriage between the members of the same *kul* and *gotro* is not allowed. According to them, the members of the same *kul* and *gotro* are brothers and sisters. This is a big sin and social crime if marriage happens among the members of the same *kul* or *gotro*. If someone commits this sin, he or she may no longer members of their village. The chief of the village has the authority to excommunicate the offenders. Moreover, Divorce, Child marriage and polygamy are also not ideal in the Deori society of Major Deori and Deori Pam village.

c. Land and Resources

The Deori tribe follows customary laws for land and resources. These laws decide how land is shared, used for farming, and how common areas like grazing fields and rivers are managed. In villages, land is usually controlled by elder councils, and rights are given according to family or village traditions. Since many Deori people live in flood-prone river areas like Majuli, their customs also include rules for shifting fields, sharing crops, and managing land together. If land disputes arise, they are first settled by the village council. Only if needed are the cases taken to formal courts. The Deori Autonomous Council also officially recognizes these traditional land practices.

d. Other offences

The Deori people believe that the Cow is a sacred animal. They intensely worship this calm animal on the first day of *Bohaag* (the month of April-May). For that reason they intensely believe that killing or making injury to this sacred animal is a great sin. If someone intentionally or mistakenly making hurt to their sacred animal, he or she should pay fine and must regret for this sin by taking *tongloti paat* (a kind of leaf) in his hand and *shantijol* from the *puruhit* of *Deoghor*. On the other hand anyone is excommunicated from their village and society if he or she intentionally kills a cow. His duration of punishment depends upon the age of the cow which is killed by him. Some of the common civil offences in these villages which have been come up for decision before the village council include public nuisance, drunken quarrels, disputes between neighbors, dispute involving agricultural land, antisocial work etc. But now a days, if the people not happy with the decisions of their village chiefs and elderly persons or cannot be settled by the elders, they usually go to the court.

Role and Importance of customary law among the Deori of Majuli

Every ethnic or cultural group tries to uphold the sequence of peace and order in their society. The Deori tribal society is also indifferent to it and therefore still they follow traditional rules and regulations. From the field investigation it is revealed that the elders of both the two Deori villages of Majuli believe that the only way of maintaining their society is to hold tightly the traditional customs and practices. They also believe that their customs and practices were laid down by their ancestors and the soul of their ancestors would be annoyed if the descendants do not obey their traditions. They have extremely faith in God and customs and never want to break their traditional rules. According to them, God's justice is far best and unlimited than the justice given by society. So that for every antisocial works and crimes the criminals must repent in front of their God (in *Deoghor*). A person who has committed a severe crime is bound to incur the wrath of God. This is the grounds why customary law is important to Deori tribe and continues to be obeyed generation after generation. From the field investigation it is revealed that

customary laws are playing a significant role in the four areas of the Deori society of Maajor Deori and Deori Pam village of Majuli:

Protection of traditional knowledge: It has been revealed that the people of the two villages believe that customary law can preserve their traditional knowledge. Customs are treasury of culture, tradition, knowledge, morals of a tribal group. It is also considered as mechanism for governing and protecting traditional knowledge and culture.

Justice for all: According to the villagers, customary laws can give justice to all. Their customary laws never determine differences between male and female. Nature and yardstick of punishments are same for all.

It governs human behavior: According to the elders of the two villages, customary laws highly govern the behavior of the people. After committing a crime a person never get a higher social position.

Mechanism of social control: The study has been also revealed that customary law is one of the major mechanisms of social control.

Conclusion

From the elucidation of the study, it can be clearly outlined that customary laws have been playing an influential role in the life the Deori tribe of the both two villages. They strongly believe that customary laws can preserve their traditional knowledge, culture, morals and govern their social life. The study shows that the Deori tribe considers customary laws as intrinsic to their identity and part and parcel of their culture and tradition. It has been playing a big role in keeping peace and order in their villages. But, expansion of modern education, new mobility and exposure to statutory legal norms influence younger generation's thoughts and they prefer legal remedies and state administrative processes over dispute settlement. The Deori Autonomous Council that established under state legislation – *Deori Autonomous Council Act, 2005*, has

special authorization to protect Deori social practices, customary laws, culture and economic interests. The existence of such an autonomous body means existence of a bridge between customary practices and state administration.

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